

A CROSS-SECTIONAL STUDY TO DETERMINE THE RESULTS OF SPINAL TUMOR SURGERY

Dr. Mukarram Nooraldeen Musarhad

M.B.Ch.B., F.I.C.M.S. (Neurosurgery), Iraqi Ministry of Health, Kirkuk Health Directorate, Azadi Teaching Hospital, Kirkuk, Iraq

Dr. Salih Adham Salih

M.B.Ch.B., F.I.C.M.S. (Neurosurgery), Iraqi Ministry of Health, Kirkuk Health Directorate, Azadi Teaching Hospital, Kirkuk, Iraq

Dr. Sarmad Abdullah Hussein

M.B.Ch.B., F.I.C.M.S. (Neurosurgery), Iraqi Ministry of Health, Kirkuk Health Directorate, Azadi Teaching Hospital, Kirkuk, Iraq

Abstract: Background: Spinal tumours are a prevalent occurrence, causing significant distress and morbidity. They are a leading cause of mortality, often resulting in radicular pain or localised pain in conjunction with neurological deficits such as the inability to use a limb. **Objective:** Our study was interested to determine and assess surgical findings of patients who underwent spinal tumor surgery. **Patients and methods:** Surgical and demographic data of patients with spinal tumors were recruited, including 87 patients who underwent tumor resection surgery. Data was collected for patients with spinal tumors from different hospitals in Iraq for a period ranging from April 8, 2022, to December 20, 2023. We conducted a set of questionnaires to evaluate the extent of pain, quality of life, and neurological status of patients after surgery. **Results:** Our outcomes found males had 65.52% of cases and females had 34.48% of cases; the most common illnesses, hypertension got, 82.76% of cases, obesity got 73.56% of cases; current smokers were 50 cases; the most histopathology common were schwannoma was 42.53% cases, and meningiomas was 34.48% cases, locations of spinal tumors were cervical spine had 16 cases, the thoracic spine had 44 cases, and lumbar spine had 27 cases, operation time was 660.23 ± 201.54 min, estimated blood loss was 95.16 ± 62.89 mL, length of stay in hospital was 6.3 ± 2.6 days, ICU admission was 2 cases, the mortality rate was no cases, rate of complications had 18 cases. **Conclusion:** Our study shows that microsurgical resection can be highly effective in treating spinal tumors and improving patient outcomes, where this technique allows for more precise and thorough removal of the tumor, reducing the risk of complications and recurrence.

Keywords: Spinal tumours; Complications; Quality of life; and Tumor resection surgery.

Introduction

Cancer is the world's second-leading cause of death. The spine was the third most prevalent location for metastatic illness, behind the lung and the liver [1]. The first diagnosed tumors are mostly breast, lung, prostate, thyroid, and kidney, but in 13% of cases, the original tumor is unknown [2]. Metastases, on the

opposite, are the most common type of bone tumor, with the spine serving as their primary site. Most spinal metastases arise in middle-aged and elderly individuals. [3]

Spinal tumors are classified into three types based on their anatomical distribution: extradural, intradural-extramedullary, and intramedullary [4]. Most metastases are located within the extradural compartment, or which includes the bony spine and epidural area [5]. They are commonly seen within vertebral bodies and extend to the pedicles. The thoracic spine is the most plagued part (70%), followed by the lumbar (20%), cervical, and sacral (10%). [6,7]

Based on the bone marrow composition and substantial vascularization, metastases first infiltrate the spinal column before spreading to the posterior arch [8]. The most common way to spread was hematogenous, with direct, lymphatic, and subarachnoid expansions being rare [9]. The venous pathway, particularly the paravertebral plexus in Batson, appears to be more essential than the arterial route. [10,11]

Arterial metastases are frequently seen around the vertebral plates, whereas malignancies that spread via Batson's spinal venous plexus impact the posterior portion of a vertebral body [12-14]. The spongy bone is penetrated first, followed by the cortical bone, which promotes pathological fracture and vertebral instability. [15]

Spine metastases can cause axial discomfort and functional restrictions as a result on pathological fractures [15]. They are often accompanied with a mass of soft tissue, which causes radicular as well as medullary epidural involvement, resulting in radiculopathy and myelopathy. 10% of people with vertebral metastases suffer from spinal cord compression. [16]

Patients and methods

We conducted a cross-sectional study on 87 patients who had spinal tumors who obtained tumor resection surgery at different hospitals in Iraq on April 8, 2022, and December 20, 2023.

All patients' clinic, demographic information, imaging modalities, surgical procedures, neuropathological diagnosis, postoperative follow-up and problems, and postoperative neurological statuses were scrutinised and collected from hospital records.

Patients were eligible to be involved in the study if they were all those who had been found on the basis of magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), operated on for spinal tumors, and confirmed histopathologically.

Patients who were excluded from our analysis included the ones who received biopsy as a diagnostic procedure as compared to (rather than) MRI or were opt for surgery as their removals had CT findings suggestive of the presence of tumor. We further excluded those patients who never underwent surgery, although they had the diagnosis done by radiology and transferred to the cancer treatment because of it.

MRI was used to evaluate all patients prior to surgery. An early postoperative MRI was done to check the remaining tumor (within 24 hours). Control MRIs were done post-operatively, with a specialist radiologist and a neurosurgeon examining any recurrent cases.

The International Frankel Scale (FS) was used to evaluate the neurological condition of each patient during presentation, early postoperative phase, and last follow-up. By using FS values collected before the operation and at follow-up consultations, FR was able to be determined. An assessment about whether their FS scores had gone up or come down decided whether a patient was better or worse off from it—functional status.

The patients were treated under general anesthesia using a posterior, posterolateral, and anterior approach. We used simple decompression, intradural tumor excision by laminoplasty, posterior stabilization by decompression, corpectomy, posterior stabilization using the posterior route, and anterior corpectomy.

We have employed the use of SPSS 22.0 statistical tool in our research. Apart from the descriptive statistical methods, demographic characteristics of cases were portrayed in percentages, means, standard deviations and through crosstabs analysis. Data having a normal distribution were analyzed using an independent sample t test. The normality for the distribution was identified using the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. The Pearson correlation test is used in the correlation analysis. P-values < 0.05 were deemed statistically significant.

Results

Table 1: Enroll demographic data of patients with spinal tumor.

Features	Number of patients [n = 87]	Percentage [%]
Age		
25 – 35	14	16.09%
36 – 45	20	22.99%
46 – 55	25	28.74%
56 - 65	28	32.18%
Sex		
Male	57	65.52%
Female	30	34.48%
BMI, Kg/m ²		
< 20.5	11	12.64%
20.5 – 24.5	34	39.08%
> 24.5	42	48.28%
Comorbidities		
Hypertension	72	82.76%
Obesity	64	73.56%
Asthma	12	13.79%
High Cholesterol	56	64.37%
Kidney disease	32	36.78%
Heart failure	20	22.99%
ASA classification		
I	14	16.09%
II	40	45.98%
III	33	37.93%
Smoking status		
Yes	50	57.47%
No	37	42.53%
Education status		
Primary	6	6.90%
Secondary	9	10.34%
College/University	24	27.59%
Post – graduated	48	55.17%
Employment status		
Working	65	74.71%
Not working	22	25.29%
Income status, \$		
< 800	54	62.07%

800 – 1100	20	22.99%
> 1100	13	14.94%

Table 2: Identify diagnoses outcomes related to spinal tumor.

Characteristics	Number of patients [n = 87]	Percentage [%]
Histopathology		
Schwannoma	37	42.53%
Meningiomas	30	34.48%
Psammomatous meningioma	14	16.09%
Transitional meningioma	8	9.20%
Atypical meningioma	6	6.90%
Anaplastic meningioma	2	2.30%
Ependymomas	13	14.94%
Myxopapillary ependymoma	7	8.05%
Sub-ependymoma	4	4.60%
Anaplastic Ependymoma	2	2.30%
Chordomas	7	8.05%
Severity of disease		
Mild	13	14.94%
Moderate	30	34.48%
Severe	44	50.57%
Locations of tumors		
Cervical spine	16	18.39%
Thoracic spine	44	50.57%
Lumbar spine	27	31.03%

Table 3: Surgical findings.

Variables	Number of patients [n = 87]	Percentage [%]
Operation time, min	660.23 ± 201.54	
General anesthesia	87	100%
Estimated blood loss, mL	95.16 ± 62.89	
Bleeding, n [%]		
Yes	4	4.6%
No	83	95.4%
Length of stay in hospital, days	6.3 ± 2.6	
ICU admission		
Yes	2	2.30%
No	85	97.70%
Mortality rate		
Yes	0	0%
No	87	87%

Figure 1: A conducting Kaplan-Meier graph in the estimation of survival - life for patients after spinal tumor surgery.

Table 4: Postoperative complications.

Complications	Number of patients [n = 87]	Percentage [%]
Infection	9	10.34%
Bleeding	2	2.30%
Nerve damage	0	0%
Spinal fluid leakage	3	3.45%
Blood clots	2	2.3%
Issues with wound healing	2	2.3%
Total	18	20.69%

Table 5: Assessment of clinical outcomes of patients in before and after tumor resection surgery.

Items	Before surgery	After surgery
Pain NRS (Numeric Rating Scale)	8.40 ± 1.72	1.53 ± 0.95
Oswestry Disability Index (ODI)	60.26 ± 8.31	12.57 ± 4.86
EQ5D5L-U	26.55 ± 7.47	84.38 ± 8.62

Table 6: Assessment of quality of life for patients after surgery by EORTC QLQ-C30 scale.

Items	Scores
Physical function	82.17 ± 10.68
Psychological function	77.60 ± 5.56
Emotional and social functions	72.16 ± 6.84
Daily activity	80.82 ± 9.67

Discussion

Spinal tumors occur seldom but frequently in neurosurgery. These conditions are deadly and unpleasant. They lead to chronic disability, dependence on drugs, and a huge financial burden that may be accompanied by psychological stress. [17]

Significantly important is the use of clinical scores based on neurological function for assessing surgical prognosis. According to some studies, the most vital prognostic indicator comes from the patient's position regarding functionality during treatment. [18]

According to some studies, about two-thirds to over four-fifths of all cases witnessed impairment of movement. A lower level of incidence of disordered urination (13.9 percent) was registered in our study versus the figures reported earlier in other reports [19]. The most commonly used diagnostic mode, MRI, is used centering radiological proceedings on the location categorization for tumors. Early MRI upon the patients versus control MRI is a crucial relapse/rogression indicator for such people. [20]

Overall, secondary (metastatic) tumors are the most common spinal tumors and are usually extradural. This is why the spinal region is the third most affected site by metastatic tumors, following the liver and the lung [21]. The incident of spinal metastasis goes on increasing throughout their sickness due to the extended lifetime of the majority of cancer patients (20-40%), with about 20% being symptomatic. [22]

In the literature, the most significant reason is that the study did not include patients who had not undergone surgery, had been operated on using interventional techniques of biopsy, or were treated with oncology/radiation oncology. [23]

Spinal cord cancer patients are unusual in nature. It is believed that there are more cases of intradural extramedullary tumours than those inside the spinal cord substance. The main aim of surgery aimed at partial extraction involves providing a sample for making a conclusive diagnosis and opening up the court as safely as possible while stabilizing any instability along the way. [24]

Several recent studies show that in terms of prognosis and outcomes, laminoplasty is better than decompressive laminectomy. Surgical treatment of spinal tumors can result into instability, hence necessitating the use of stabilization methods. Thus, more aggressive surgical strategies can be required in the presence of severe instability or deformity. [25]

Conclusion

Microsurgical resection surgery can be less invasive than other procedures, resulting in fewer stays in the hospital, faster recovery periods, and better overall patient results. It may help to protect the underlying healthy tissue as well as nerves, decreasing the probability of damage along with post-operative issues.

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